

PHA AND PLA DISPERSIONS AS BIODEGRADABLE SEALING LACQUERS FOR PAPER-BASED BARRIER PACKAGING

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Abstract: *The shortage of biodegradable options for sealing lacquers for paper-based packaging has led to research on biopolyesters like PLA and PHA, though both pose challenges due to their high crystallinity and melting temperatures, complicating film formation at lower coating temperatures. In our research, we addressed these challenges by using low crystalline polymer grades in an emulsification/solvent evaporation process, resulting in dispersions characterised by small particle sizes in the range of 220-510 nm and effective film formation at reduced temperatures of maximum 150 °C. Coated papers showed strong barrier performance, with WVTR and oxygen permeance values below 20 g/m²-d and 1 cm³/m²-d-bar, respectively. While PLA-based coatings achieved acceptable seal strengths, PHA coatings require further optimization. The potential for use in food packaging applications was confirmed by overall migration below regulatory limits and sensory tests on chocolate showing no differences to the conventional packaging over the given shelf-life.*

Keywords: paper packaging, biopolymer, polymer dispersion, barrier coating, sealing

1 INTRODUCTION

The shift towards sustainable packaging is a crucial endeavour for our society today, particularly in the transition from plastic to paper packaging. One of the main challenges lies in developing reliable barriers that can effectively protect the contents of the package. Conventional coatings like polyolefins and acrylates are petroleum-based, non-biodegradable, and difficult to recycle (Kunam et al. 2022), making them poorly suitable for single-use applications. Biobased materials such as proteins and polysaccharides offer good oxygen barriers, but struggle with moisture resistance and sealability. Thermoplastic biopolymers like PLA and PHAs are promising alternatives.

For practical use in paper coatings, water-based formulations are preferred due to easier handling and lower emissions. However, formulating these biopolymers into dispersions presents additional challenges. The film-forming temperature for dispersion lacquers typically falls between the glass transition and melting temperatures of the polymer, indicating that the amorphous parts of the polymer form the closed barrier layer. Standard PLA and PHA grades exhibit high crystallinities that limit film formation, often requiring processing temperatures above their melting point, which is not economically feasible. In particular, the crystalline nature of the PHB copolymers available on the market, such as PHBV, of almost 60% with a low hydroxy valerate content has disadvantages such as high melting points between 160-180 °C, inherent brittleness and a narrow processing window, which limit their large-scale application (Wu et al. 2021). Thus, it is essential to explore alternative grades and

formulation techniques to achieve efficient film formation at temperatures at least below 150 °C that can be processed more easily on paper coating lines.

To address this, we developed water-based dispersions using an emulsification/solvent evaporation process with low-crystallinity polymer grades. This paper presents the preparation and upscaling of PLA and PHA dispersions in a multilayer coating approach, along with packaging-relevant characterizations.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Paper substrates were the one-side coated packaging paper PackPro 7.0 at a grammage of 80 gsm and the barrier paper NiklaBarr Base at a grammage of 88 gsm, both from Brigl & Bergmeister GmbH. Polymers used for dispersion preparation were the amorphous PLA Luminy® LX930 and LX975 from TotalEnergies Corbion and a PHB-copolymer PHBHHx provided by HPX Polymers. Other PHAs tested for their film formation were the Green Planet™ X331N PHBH by Kaneka Belgium and the PHI 003 PHBV from Natureplast. The polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH) used as a 10 wt% aqueous solution for precoating was the Exceval AQ-4104 from Kuraray. During the formulation process, chloroform and ethyl acetate from VWR chemicals were used as solvents for the polymers, and 0.5 wt% aqueous solution of polyvinyl alcohol ($M_w = 9000\text{--}10000$ g/mol, Sigma Aldrich) was used for stabilization of droplets/particles.

2.2 Dispersion preparation

Polymer particles were obtained by the solvent evaporation method combined with the miniemulsion technique using the adapted procedure described in Musyanovych et al. 2008. Briefly, 0.4 g of polymer was dissolved in 10 g of chloroform (or 8 g ethyl acetate in the case of PLA Luminy® LX930 and LX975). The macroemulsion was prepared by adding 24 g of an 0.5 wt% PVA solution to the organic phase, and subsequent magnetic stirring of the mixture at 900 rpm for 60 min. Afterwards, the macroemulsion was subjected to ultrasonication under ice cooling for 180 s at 70% amplitude in a pulse regime (30 s sonication, 10 s pause) using a Branson 450 W sonifier and ¼" tip. The obtained miniemulsion was transferred to the 50 ml reaction flask with a large size neck and left overnight at 40 °C for a complete evaporation of the organic solvent. This general procedure was realized in various project phases using different batch sizes, depending on the individual requirements in each project phase. For Roll-to-Roll trials the obtained aqueous dispersions were concentrated up to 30 wt% solid content by removing water in a rotary evaporator at 40 °C.

2.3 Paper Coating

Sheet coating. Preliminary tests on film formation and barrier properties were conducted using a lab-scale coating unit (CUF 5, Sumet Messtechnik) with a convection dryer and k-bar technique. To achieve dry coating thicknesses of 4–8 µm, k-bars with varying wet layer thicknesses were selected based on each dispersion's solid content. Minimum film formation temperature (MFFT) was evaluated on transparent oPET (Hostaphan, 23 µm) by assessing coating transparency and scratch resistance across temperatures from 90–160 °C. The same parameters were applied to paper substrates.

Multilayer approach. To combine functionalities, a PVOH precoat was applied for planarization and oxygen barrier, followed by a PLA or PHA topcoat for water vapor barrier and sealability.

Roll-to-roll coating. Multilayer structures were produced on a pilot-scale lacquering line (Fraunhofer IVV, Freising) using a slot-die system (FMP Technology). The die had a width of 260 mm, gap length of

45 mm, and shim thickness of 100 μm . Wet layer thicknesses were adjusted to achieve target dry coating weights of 4 gsm (precoat) and 7 gsm (topcoat).

Figure 1: Multilayer barrier concept

2.4 Sample characterization

Particle Morphology. The morphology of produced particles was studied by scanning electron microscopy (zeiss leo 1550 vp, acceleration voltage 1 kv). A drop of diluted sample was dried on a silicon wafer at room temperature and sputtered with gold to enhance electron density contrast.

Particle Size. Dynamic light scattering was conducted on water diluted samples using a Malvern Zetasizer Ultra-Red at 173° (backscattering option); analysed based on cumulants analysis (Malvern General Purpose Algorithm).

Oxygen Permeance. Measured per DIN 53380-3 using an OX-TRAN 2/21 OTR Analyzer (Ametek Mocon) at 23 °C, 50% RH. Measurements were taken until permeation stabilized for at least 10 h; duplicates were performed.

Water Vapor Transmission Rate. Determined gravimetrically per DIN 53122-1. Samples were weighed initially and stored at 23 °C, 85% RH in a climate chamber. Weight gain was tracked four times in 48 h until it stagnated; four replicates per specimen were tested.

Heat Sealability. Packaging was sealed using a Brugger HSG-C. Sealing parameters (temperature, pressure and time) differed depending on the dispersion coating as indicated in the results section. Sealed-seam strength was tested per DIN 55 529 at 90° pull-off, 50 N, 100 mm/min on 15 mm strips.

Migration Testing. Total migration was tested using Tenax[®] (food simulant E) for dry foods. 1 dm² coated paper from roll-to-roll trials was exposed to 4 g Tenax[®] for 10 days at 40 °C (coating = food contact side). After 3-fold extracted with diethyl ether; the residue was weighed to determine overall migration (mg/dm²).

Sensory Testing. Chocolate bars were re-packed in coated paper from the roll-to-roll trials and heat-sealed (sachet packaging). Both originally and re-packed samples were stored at 23 °C, 50% RH. Repeated triangle tests (DIN EN ISO 4120-2007) with a non-trained panel (n=16) were performed to assess perceptual sensory differences.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Dispersion characteristics

The particle sizes and respective PDI values obtained by DLS measurements for representative dispersion samples are summarized in Table 1. The morphology of the particles obtained was analysed using SEM. The selected representative images are shown in Figure 2. All produced particles are spherical in shape, except PHBV nanoparticles. Due to the high crystallinity of PHBV, the obtained particles have irregular shape. The average diameter varies in the range between 220 and 510 nm.

Compared to PHBHHx particles, the surface of PLA particles is smoother and looks harder, which is mainly due to the difference in T_g values for both polymers. The dispersions produced from ethyl acetate as solvent possess smaller particle size in comparison to those obtained from chloroform.

Table 1: DLS measurement results of produced biopolymer particle dispersions

Polymer	Grade	Solvent	Particle size [nm]	PDI
PLA	Luminy® LX975	Chloroform	434	0.21
PLA	Luminy® LX930	Chloroform	510	0.18
PHBV	PHI 003	Chloroform	413	0.25
PHBH	Green Planet™ X331N	Chloroform	423	0.24
PHBHHx	-	Chloroform	369	0.26
PLA	Luminy® LX975	Ethyl acetate	325	0.39
PLA	Luminy® LX930	Ethyl acetate	223	0.23

Figure 2: Representative SEM images of selected biopolymer particle dispersions; PLA Luminy® LX975 (a), PHBV (b) and PHBHHx (c)

3.2 Preliminary studies on film formation

To find suitable polymer grades that offer film formation at temperatures <150 °C, different PLA and PHA types (Table 2) were screened. Only low-crystallinity grades enabled successful film formation below their melting points. According to latex film formation theory, the MFFT is closely related to the T_g and usually lies closely above it (Keddie und Routh 2010). For the semi-crystalline standard polymer grades used in this study, film formation only in the amorphous regions was not sufficient to obtain particle deformation and film formation to obtain a continuous polymer layer. Therefore, we prefer grades with low crystallinity and lower molecular weights. This choice is also beneficial regarding the dispersion preparation step, since less toxic solvents than chloroform such as ethyl acetate can be used.

Table 2: Tested polymers and their properties. MFFT = Minimum film forming temperature. Information on biodegradability is provided by the manufacturer.

Polymer	Grade	Biodegradability	M_w [kg/mol]	T_g [°C]	T_m [°C]	X_c [%]	MFFT [°C]
PLA	LX930	Industrially Compostable ¹	160	60	130**	0	90
PLA	LX975	Industrially Compostable ¹	180	60	130**	0	90
PHBV	PHI 003	Industrially Compostable ²	315	0	165	64*	>160***
PHBH	X331N	Industrially ¹ and Home ³ Compostable, Marine ⁴ and Soil ⁵ Biodegradable	260	0	135 / 150	40*	160
PHBHHx	-	no data available, comparable to PHBH based on chemical similarity	185	0	63 / 105	15*	90

^{*} ΔH_{ref} (PHB) = 146 J/g (Barham et al. 1984), ^{**}Flow point, ^{***}no film formation after convectional drying, but with hot press at 170 °C
¹certified by TÜV Austria (OK Compost INDUSTRIAL), ²according to manufacturer information on <https://natureplast.eu/de/produit/pha/>,
³certified by TÜV Austria (OK Compost HOME), ⁴according to manufacturer information on <https://kanekaqaagreenplanet.com/>, ⁵certified by TÜV Austria (OK Compost SOIL)

3.3 Barrier and sealing properties of coated papers

To estimate the theoretical barrier potential of our dispersion coatings, ideal WVTR values were calculated based on known permeation rates for PLA and PHBHHx films. For PHBHHx, a WVTR of $\sim 9 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ at $100 \mu\text{m}$ thickness suggests a theoretical value of $\sim 90 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ for a $10 \mu\text{m}$ coating. Similarly, PLA with $\sim 25 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ at $100 \mu\text{m}$ would yield $\sim 250 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ at $10 \mu\text{m}$. These values represent defect-free coatings and do not account for substrate or precoat effects, coating imperfections or other interactions during water vapour permeation.

Table 3: Overview of coated samples, their barrier and sealing properties.

Sample description		WVTR 23 °C, 85 % RH	OP 23 °C, 50% RH		Grammage (approx. coating weight)	Medium Force	Maximum Force	Application	
Layer structure	Substrate	$\text{g}/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d})$	$\text{cm}^3/(\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d}\cdot\text{bar})$		gsm	N/15mm	N/15mm		
1	PP7/PLA	PP7 80 gsm	140 ± 3.40	-	-	86.6 (8)	1.68 ± 0.28^1	2.83 ± 0.51^1	sheet
2	PP7/PVOH/PLA	PP7 80 gsm	150 ± 0.5	0.144	$\frac{0.76}{1}$	91.92 (4.5+7.5)	1.78 ± 0.19^1	2.52 ± 0.39^1	roll-to-roll
3	NB/PVOH/PLA	NB 88 gsm	19.5 ± 1.23	<ML	$\frac{0.69}{4}$	101.29 (4.5+8)	-	3.39 ± 0.30^1	roll-to-roll
4	PP7/PHBHHx	PP7 80 gsm	151 ± 2.5	136	130	95.5 (15.5)	1.40 ± 0.29^3	2.06 ± 0.44^3	sheet
5	NB/PHBHHx	NB 88 gsm	24.1 ± 0.57	590	661	96.35 (8)	0.83 ± 0.61^2	1.17 ± 0.15^2	sheet
6	PP7/PVOH/PHBHHx	PP7 80 gsm	90.3 ± 6.02	161	164	85.84 (2+6)	1.38 ± 0.03^2	1.98 ± 0.16^2	sheet
7	PP7/PVOH/PHBHHx	PP7 80 gsm	119 ± 1.5	0.616	2495	85.17 (4+3)	0.50 ± 0.23^4	0.75 ± 0.29^4	sheet
8	NB/PVOH/PHBHHx	NB 88 gsm	17.6 ± 0.15	1.02	1.3	96.21 (4+4)	0.14 ± 0.04^4	0.20 ± 0.05^4	roll-to-roll

¹ 150 °C / 5 bar / 2 sec; paper tear; ² 130 °C / 5 bar / 0.5 sec; partial delamination from substrate/precoat; ³ 130 °C / 5 bar / 0.5 sec; paper tear; ⁴ 150 °C / 5 bar / 2 sec, delamination from substrate/precoat

Table 3 shows the barrier values as well as sealing strengths achieved for our samples. All dispersion tested were produced using chloroform and PLA dispersion refer to the LX930 grade. Both barrier and sealing performances vary with coating quality and thickness.

Measured WVTR values approached these theoretical limits, with PLA reaching $140 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ and PHBHHx $90 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ on PP7. Using the precoated substrate NB, significantly lower WVTRs ($< 20 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$) were achieved (structures 3 and 8), although the substrate itself contributes $\sim 40 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$.

A recent study by Nissinen et al. 2025 using PLA dispersion (PLAX) and bioORMOCER[®] reported WVTRs of $260 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ for similar multilayer structures. Our best values ($\sim 150 \text{ g/m}^2\cdot\text{d}$ on PP7) compare favourably. For oxygen permeance (OP), PVOH outperformed bioORMOCER[®], achieving values $< 1 \text{ cm}^3/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d}\cdot\text{bar}$, indicating nearly defect-free coatings. In contrast, OP values in the hundreds suggest coating defects and thus rather free diffusion of oxygen, likely caused by mechanical stress during multilayer application or sample handling. PHBHHx also showed moderate oxygen barrier properties, with structure 4 reaching $\sim 130 \text{ cm}^3/\text{m}^2\cdot\text{d}\cdot\text{bar}$.

Beyond barrier properties, biopolyester coatings also offer grease resistance (Basak et al. 2024) and enable heat sealing. PLA's low flow point allowed effective sealing at $120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, with optimal results at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Structure 3 achieved a maximum seal strength of $\sim 3.4 \text{ N}/15 \text{ mm}$, with paper tear observed in all samples. PHBHHx coatings showed lower seal strengths ($\leq 2 \text{ N}/15 \text{ mm}$), often accompanied by delamination, indicating a need for improved adhesion and optimized sealing parameters.

A minimum of 5 gsm coating is recommended to ensure acceptable performance, as demonstrated by structures 9 and 10, which differ only in PHBHHx coating weight but show significant variation, although mentioned delamination effects have a great influence on the measured values.

Compared to conventional PE-based sealing lacquers (> 6 N/25 mm; Merabtene et al. 2023), our seal strengths are lower. The S-POP structure discussed by Nissinen et al. 2025 achieved 4.1 N/25 mm under optimized conditions (170 °C, 2 s, 800 N), comparable to our results when accounting for sample size differences. They attributed reduced sealability to foaming and bubble formation during coating. Despite degassing, residual bubbles may have affected our results as well. To improve seal seam strength, further reduction of foaming—via defoaming agents and optimized degassing—is recommended, along with refinement of sealing parameters.

3.4 Food contact evaluation and migration testing

Materials and articles intended for food contact must comply with the general safety requirements outlined in Article 3 of Framework Regulation (EC) No. 1935/2004, which ensures that substances do not endanger human health, alter food composition, or impair sensory properties. Plastic materials are further regulated under Commission Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011, which includes a Union list of authorized substances and sets specific migration limits (SMLs) and an overall migration limit (OML) of 10 mg/dm² of food contact surface. This limit represents the maximum allowable release of non-volatile substances from packaging into food. For non-plastic materials, such as paper or coatings, national recommendations from the German Federal Institute for Risk Assessment (BfR) can apply.

All biopolyesters used in this study—PLA, PHBV, and PHBH—are authorized for food contact under Regulation (EU) No. 10/2011. For PHBH oligomers ($M_w < 1000$ Da), a specific migration limit (SML) of 5 mg/kg food must not be exceeded. Furthermore, the SML of 0.05 mg/kg food for crotonic acid must be considered (Silano et al. 2019), which also applies for degradation products of PHBV. In the case of polyvinyl alcohol (PVOH), vinyl acetate—its monomer—is subject to an SML of 12 mg/kg food.

In this study, overall migration testing was conducted prior to sensory evaluation. Using Tenax[®] as a food simulant, measured migration values were consistently below 1 mg/dm², significantly under the regulatory limit of 10 mg/dm². These results confirm the suitability of the tested coatings for food contact applications.

3.4 Sensorical testing

To assess whether chocolate bars packed in the paper-based packaging differed perceptibly from those in the original metallized film, triangle tests were conducted at 3, 7, 11, 15, and 20 weeks—covering the product’s shelf life. With $n = 16$, a minimum of 8 correct identifications is required to confirm a perceptible difference ($\alpha > 0.20$). A correct answer corresponds to an identified difference between the original and paper packed product. Panellists indicated whether their choice was based on certainty or guessing. Table 4 shows correct answers given for each test. Based on this, no perceptible differences were determined, and there is also no trend indicating that product differences arise due to the respective packaging over the storage period.

Table 4: Results of the triangle test

Layer structure	3 Weeks	7 Weeks	11 Weeks	16 Weeks	20 Weeks
2 PP7/PVOH/PLA	7/16 3 guesses	3/16 1 guess	5/16 4 guesses	6/16 1 guess	5/16 1 guess
3 NB/PVOH/PLA	5/16 3 guesses	4/16 4 guesses	5/16 3 guesses	6/16 3 guesses	5/16 1 guess

Even though the WVTR values between structure 3 (< 20 g/(m²·d)) and structure 2 (150 g/(m²·d)) vary greatly, no sensory differences were detected. For chocolate products, internal results showed that especially light and aroma barrier is needed to maintain food quality (ChocoPack 2022-2024), while moderate water vapor and oxygen barriers might be sufficient to prevent texture changes or sugar bloom as well as oxidation of fats. Although often claimed as being closely related, aroma and oxygen

concentrations showed complicated relationships regarding oxygen dependence when investigated for rapeseed oil (Andersson und Lingnert 1999). They observed that storage at lower oxygen levels could even lead to more off-flavour in the product, especially during very early stages of oxidation. However, these small differences between samples when oxidation proceeds very slowly may not be detected by sensory evaluation. Compared to rapeseed oil, oxidation processes on the surface of chocolate bars should even be more slowly and therefore sensory differences are unlikely to occur during the product's shelf life.

In terms of aroma barrier properties, PLA could offer notable advantages in aroma protection compared to conventional polyolefins. Due to its low diffusivity for organic molecules, PLA acts as a low-permeability polymer, effectively limiting the migration of volatile compounds into or out of the packaging (Ewender et al. 2025). As Ducruet et al. 2011 further highlight, PLA displays promising barrier properties especially towards hydrophobic aroma compounds.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms the potential of water-based PLA and PHA dispersions for sustainable paper packaging. Low-crystallinity polymer grades enabled film formation below 150 °C and allow the potential use of less harmful solvents, which can also be beneficial for processing at higher scale. Multilayer structures significantly improved oxygen water vapor barrier properties, achieving values close to theoretical limits given by the polyesters. While PLA-based coatings showed moderate seal strength, PHA samples used in this study require further optimization, especially regarding the adhesion on substrate and precoating. Sensory results indicate that PLA coatings are particularly suitable for aroma-sensitive products like chocolate, helping preserve flavour integrity throughout the shelf life. Overall, the approach offers a biodegradable food packaging alternative, though improvements in sealing performance and process stability are still needed for industrial application.

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